

THE AFFECT OF CLEAR INSTRUCTIONS IN LANGUAGE
TEACHING

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Abstract: This article will explain the effect of clear instructions in language teaching. Will describe the problem on this topic with the theory of linguists. Special experiments of different methods will be used for this purpose. And the results of these experiments will be shown.

Keywords: clear instructions, special experiments, language teaching.

Introduction

An instructions is a document that explains the ways or rules for performing certain actions. Nowadays, explaining something to students just by explaining it to them will not give them clear results. To do this is necessary to give the right instructions to the learner's to get good results. To Scrivener (2005, p. 90), unplanned instructions on sounds "like a joke" as teachers "are often unaware that they are talking in this way." When the teacher prepares the lesson planned and gives the right instructions, the students remember everything much better. When they reconsider what they have taught via recording either a video or an audio script for themselves, they realize how confusing they have been. Scrivener (ibid.) argues that unplanned instruction in EFL classrooms would definitely hinder students' understanding as "the essential information about what to do is embedded in confusing and unnecessary babble." It is so obvious that giving instructions to students is not an easy task because the teacher should be a master of the know-how to do that, otherwise 'the best activity in the world is a waste of time if the

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students do not understand what they are supposed to do” (Harmer, 1998, p. 4). They face difficulties in understanding the point taught not because they are lazy or not paying attention to the teacher, but simply because the instructions are ineffective. Similarly, Scrivener (2005, p. 90) argues that “an essentially simple activity can become impossible, not because the students could not do it, but because they did not understand what to do”. Instructions and their delivery can be the determining factors as to whether a lesson succeeds or fails (Scrivener 2011;Ur 1996). According to Ur (1996, 16), research indicates “that learners see the ability to explain things well as one of the most important qualities of a good teacher.” For example, Wragg and Wood’s (1984, 82) research found that the teacher’s “ability to explain is most highly valued.”

If the instruction is unplanned, however, it can be a serious problem for students' understanding

Method

The article provides an example of data collection, which is carried out using the method of qualitative research. The data was collected by observation. Observation is a special process of consciousness of the object of reality the result of which is recorded in the description for obtaining significant results. The observation method was chosen to make the study more experimental as this method allows to see side of the nuance to be included in this article.

Two online lessons were chosen for this method of observation. These online lessons were conducted in two groups by different teachers in order to compare teachers' methods and understand the instructions used by teachers and the importance of clear instructions in language learning.

Overview

These lessons were conducted by teachers of English, whose language level reaches up to C1-C2. Professors of Higher Education who graduated with a

Master's degree. One of them Setenay Celik . She is from Turkey. She has been teaching English for 8 years.

She features a Masters Degree in English Language Teaching from Gaza University in Ankara, Turkey. The second of them Valerius Gagas. Experienced Academic Director with a demonstrated history of working in the primary/middle school industry. Skilled in Lesson Planning, Teaching English as a Second Language, Teacher Training, and Curriculum Development.

Procedure

I observed Setenay Celik's online lesson. And I saw that her lesson began with a warm-up that was attractive to students. The warm-up was a 'memory game', the teacher called one student to the board to explain the game. It showed pictures and on the back side there were other pictures. She showed pictures one by one and you need to remember the back. For example sleepy/drawer , cold/ door and so on. The student started playing the game and she remembered what picture was on the back. The warm-up was interesting.

The teacher was well prepared for the lesson and the lesson was successful. She explained how to teach little students vocabulary improving their skills. She used interesting lesson tactics and asserted that little students remember so much better.

The lesson held by Valerijus Gagas for primary school in Nanjing, China was directed to learn the language. The teacher began the lesson explaining with pictures, for example showed a picture of a boy and a girl. When he spoke the boy got up only boys and so on. The transition from one stage to the next was smooth. He started explaining the rules to them by showing them pictures and they all repeated what it meant and when they all repeated everything together, the students remembered better. In the middle of the lesson there was constant workout. The duration of the lesson was half an hour. The teacher prepared an effective lesson. And the lesson was productive.

Data analysis

In my opinion, the second lesson was more successful. Since the lesson lasted more than the first. And the transition from one stage to another went smoothly. And the first teacher explained only that the students remember the words and quickly forget them. And she did a warm-up. And the second teacher would teach them pictures, doing a workout, and they would learn the language by repeating the teacher.

Recommendation

Observed this online lesson, I was convinced of the effectiveness of the technique. I liked the way the teacher leads the lesson. I think that if you teach the second-teacher method, the learners will remember the young learners quickly and will not forget them. Because little students remember and don't forget better when they see it, touch it, and do it themselves.

If you apply the methods of the second teacher to the children everything will be clear and the lesson will be interesting

Conclusion

One conclusion that can be drawn from this research is that clear instructions will benefit the language educators. Thus , these results confirm previous studies on the positive effect (Harmer, 1998, pp 4). The results also show that the flow of learning helps students to better understand English.

Reference

Scrivener (2005,p.90), unplanned instructions.

Harmer (1998.p.4)

Scrivener(2005.p.90)

Scrivener (2011; Ur 1996)

Ur (1996,16) research indicates.

Wragg and Wood's (1984,82) research found that the teacher's

Appendix

